

Useful Numbers for Cell Culture

Useful information for various sizes of cell culture dishes and flasks

There are various sizes of dishes and flasks used for cell culture. Some useful numbers such as surface area and volumes of dissociation solutions are given below for various size culture vessels.

	Surface area (cm ²)	Seeding density*	Cells at confluency*	Trypsin (mL) approx. volume	Growth medium (mL) approx. volume
Dishes					
35 mm	8.8	0.3 x 10 ⁶	1.2 x 10 ⁶	1	2
60 mm	21.5	0.8 x 10 ⁶	3.2 x 10 ⁶	3	5
100 mm	56.7	2.2 x 10 ⁶	8.8 x 10 ⁶	5	12
150 mm	145	5.0 x 10 ⁶	20.0 x 10 ⁶	10	30
Culture plates					
6-well	9.6	0.3 x 10 ⁶	1.2 x 10 ⁶	1	1 to 3
12-well	3.5	0.1 x 10 ⁶	0.5 x 10 ⁶	0.4 to 1	1 to 2
24-well	1.9	0.05 x 10 ⁶	0.24 x 10 ⁶	0.2 to 0.3	0.5 to 1.0
48-well	1.1	0.03 x 10 ⁶	0.12 x 10 ⁶	0.1 to 0.2	0.2 to 0.4
96-well	0.32	0.01 x 10 ⁶	0.04 x 10 ⁶	0.05 to 0.1	0.1 to 0.2
Flasks					
T-25	25	0.7 x 10 ⁶	2.8 x 10 ⁶	3	3–5
T-75	75	2.1 x 10 ⁶	8.4 x 10 ⁶	5	8–15
T-175	175	4.9 x 10 ⁶	23.3 x 10 ⁶	17	35–53
T-225	225	6.3 x 10 ⁶	30 x 10 ⁶	22	45–68

*Seeding density is given for each culture vessel type as follows: Dishes and Flasks: Cells per vessel; Culture plates: Cells per well.

†The number of cells on a confluent plate, dish, or flask will vary with cell type. For this table, HeLa cells were used.